

Чэнлун Ли

Доцент. Факультет экономики и менеджмента,
Хэйхэский университет, г. Хэйхэ, провинция Хэйлуцзян, Китай.
ORCID: 0000-0002-4140-9203.

Сиаосюйэ Чжан

Преподаватель. Факультет экономики и менеджмента,
Хэйхэский университет, г. Хэйхэ, провинция Хэйлуцзян, Китай.
ORCID: 0009-0008-2780-3176.

Проблемы трансграничной электронной торговли провинции Хэйлуцзян с Россией и способы их преодоления

Исследование выполнено в рамках программы поддержки фундаментальных исследований молодых преподавателей провинции Хэйлуцзян (2024), проект «Исследование пути развития трансграничной электронной торговли провинции Хэйлуцзян с Россией в контексте цифровой экономики» (№ YQJH2024162).

Fund Project: 2024 Heilongjiang Province «Excellent Young Teachers Basic Research Support Program» General Project: «Research on the High-quality Development Path of Heilongjiang Province's Cross-border E-commerce with Russia Against the Background of Digital Economy» (YQJH2024162).

Introduction

Heilongjiang Province has achieved significant success in the rapid development of cross-border e-commerce with Russia. Heilongjiang Province is located at a key node in the “China-Mongolia-Russia” economic corridor, with unique geographical advantages and abundant resource endowments, which provide favorable conditions for its cross-border e-commerce development. In recent years, Heilongjiang Province has actively promoted the development of cross-border e-commerce with Russia, achieving significant results. Harbin, Suifenhe, Heihe and other places have become important hubs for cross-border e-commerce with Russia. Through close cooperation with the Far East region of Russia, the scale of cross-border e-commerce transactions in agricultural products, light industrial products, electronic products, and other fields in Hei-

longjiang Province has been expanding year by year. However, despite the good development momentum, there are still many challenges.

1. Problems of Heilongjiang Province's Cross-border E-commerce with Russia

1.1 Lacking Distinctive Cross-border E-commerce Platforms, and Inconspicuous Radiating and Driving Effects

In recent years, the number of e-commerce platforms in Heilongjiang Province has further increased, with the emergence of cross-border e-commerce platforms such as Real Goods Fair, Russian Goods Market, More Russian Goods, Machinery China, and China Machinery Network. The main features are focused on export-to-Russia and mechanical products. As for now, there are several cross-border e-commerce platforms with business scope covering cross-border e-commerce import, export, and cross-border e-commerce customs clearance services, effectively driving the import and export of cross-border e-commerce in Heilongjiang Province. However, in the actual development process, there are still problems of insufficient characteristic e-commerce platforms and large-scale e-commerce platforms, and a lack of pillar enterprises that can lead the development of cross-border e-commerce industry. According to the overall plan of the China(Heilongjiang) Pilot Free Trade Zone, the functional division of the three areas of Harbin, Suifenhe, and Heihe, and the implementation plan of the Harbin-Suifenhe-Heihe Cross-border E-commerce Comprehensive Pilot Zone, the characteristics of the cross-border e-commerce platform are not yet prominent enough to fully reflect the development focus and characteristics in the overall plan of the Free Trade Zone and the implementation plan of the Comprehensive Pilot Zone [1].

In addition, there is still a problem of uneven development in the e-commerce industry in Heilongjiang Province, with most cross-border e-commerce enterprises concentrated in Harbin, Suifenhe, and Heihe. This is certainly because these three areas are both free trade zones and comprehensive pilot zones for cross-border e-commerce, and the advantages of the dual zones have promoted the development of cross-border e-commerce in Harbin, Suifenhe, and Heihe. However, the radiation and driving role of these three areas in the field of cross-border e-commerce has not yet been fully utilized, and the cross-border e-commerce industry in other regions is still at a relatively low level of development. At present, cross-border e-commerce pilot zones such as Harbin, Heihe, and Suifenhe are developing rapidly, with significantly improved cross-border e-commerce service and applica-

tion capabilities, effectively promoting the agglomeration of the cross-border e-commerce industry. However, the number and scale of cross-border e-commerce enterprises settled in each pilot zone are still insufficient, and a highly influential cross-border e-commerce industry cluster has not yet been formed. Moreover, Heilongjiang Province currently lacks a group of representative and leading cross-border e-commerce enterprises and cross-border e-commerce service enterprises, which is difficult to meet the needs of driving the rapid development of the province's cross-border e-commerce industry. The main output products of cross-border e-commerce are electronic digital products and light industrial products produced in the Yangtze River Delta and Pearl River Delta regions. The added value of goods in Heilongjiang Province is relatively low and lacks market competitiveness.

1.2 Some E-commerce Companies Pursuing High Profits Unilaterally, and Lacking Punishment Mechanisms for Platform Handling

Russia's intellectual property protection is becoming increasingly strict, requiring manufacturers or sellers to prove ownership of their products' intellectual property. The penalties imposed by Russian customs on administrative violations related to intellectual property are increasing every year, and this growth trend is very evident. The severity of administrative enforcement is also increasing. A few e-commerce companies in Heihe City, in order to pursue product traffic and obtain short-term profits, sell counterfeit and inferior products on e-commerce platforms, and even illegally use traffic icons to attract customers and promote, although they have obtained high profits in a short period of time. However, in the increasingly stringent environment of the Russian e-commerce market, this approach is not advisable.

Cross-border e-commerce platforms lack a fast track mechanism for handling infringement complaints, especially due to the lack of specialized institutions for handling infringement complaints. As a result, cross-border e-commerce platforms may not be able to respond quickly to infringement complaints from rights holders, which may lead to the expansion of losses caused by infringement. At this time, cross-border e-commerce platforms face the danger of bearing joint and several liability with infringers, while also facing the possibility of expanding losses for the infringed parties [2]. Cross-border e-commerce platforms lack a punishment mechanism for companies and merchants who have previously infringed, resulting in a lack of deterrence before infringement occurs. The commercial and economic costs of infringement are low, and intentional infringement incidents cannot be effectively curbed.

1.3 Relatively Backward Informationization Level of Cross-border Logistics in Russia, and Needing Improving Efficiency of Cross-border Logistics

The development of the dual circulation pattern cannot be separated from the construction of a modern logistics system. However, from the current perspective, the cross-border logistics service capacity of Heilongjiang Province is relatively weak, which is manifested in the following aspects: Secondly, the road, railway, and air transportation routes in Heilongjiang Province are all mature, but long transportation time is still a major difficulty. Overall, it is currently difficult for cross-border logistics to achieve the operational effects of short time, high efficiency, and low cost. The insufficient technology and capacity of sea and railway transit tools result in the entire transportation process taking a long time, which affects the speed and effectiveness of transportation.

The demand in the Russian e-commerce market is huge, and cross-border online shopping products come from China. Russian consumers purchase Chinese products that are mostly of good quality and affordable. The surface mail service of postal parcels has become the most widely used logistics method for cross-border e-commerce with Russia. However, Russia has a vast territory and diversified consumption, resulting in longer delivery times for cross-border e-commerce packages in Russia. At present, it takes ten days to travel from Manzhouli in Heilongjiang Province to Russia via the China-Europe Railway, and the postal service in Russia has a slower speed, so the domestic delivery time may even be longer. The logistics efficiency needs to be further improved.

2. Specific Countermeasures of Heilongjiang Province's Cross-border E-commerce with Russia

2.1 Creating a Distinctive Cross-border E-commerce Platform and Coordinating Coordinated Development

Heilongjiang Province, as the most important agricultural province and grain base in China, has a green food certification planting area accounting for about one-fifth of China's total planting area, and has multiple green food processing enterprises, which can provide sufficient supply for online sales. Therefore, Heilongjiang Province should fully leverage its advantages in agricultural product production, utilize its regional advantages over Russia, avoid fierce competition from homogeneous platforms, and create a cross-border e-commerce platform for Russian specialty agricultural products by integrating the resources of various end platforms within the province and implementing differentiated design concepts. This platform can facili-

tate two-way agricultural product transactions, allowing not only the sale of Heilongjiang Province's specialty agricultural products to the outside world, but also the import of high-quality and affordable Russian food, making it a leading enterprise in the cross-border e-commerce platform for Russian agricultural products. The greenhouse vegetables exported from Russia are mainly tomatoes, colorful peppers, and pointed peppers, while the outdoor vegetables are mainly carrots. Shouguang's vegetables are mainly exported to Russia through Manzhouli Port located in the Nei Monggol Autonomous Region, China and Suifenhe Port located in Heilongjiang Province, China. Heilongjiang Province has many well-known domestic manufacturing enterprises and numerous innovative start-ups, with a relatively strong foundation in the manufacturing industry. However, the number of enterprises involved in cross-border e-commerce is relatively small. Against the backdrop of the country's overall acceleration of the development of cross-border e-commerce, a new form and model of foreign trade industry, the development of manufacturing enterprises in Heilongjiang Province in the field of cross-border e-commerce is relatively lagging behind. Policies or measures should be introduced to promote the transformation of manufacturing enterprises into cross-border e-commerce and create a unique sales platform [3]. There is a must to further cultivate characteristic industrial bases for cross-border e-commerce, create cross-border e-commerce industry clusters, and promote the sales model of "regional industrial belt cross-border e-commerce". There is also a must to enhance the core competitiveness of enterprises, thereby forming a foreign trade brand effect, in order to promote the transformation of foreign trade from quantity expansion to quality improvement.

Taking the construction of Harbin, Heihe, and Suifenhe Cross-border E-commerce Comprehensive Pilot Zones as a breakthrough point, it is necessary to comprehensively integrate cross-border e-commerce resources such as industrial parks, comprehensive bonded zones, and border warehouses, introduce support policies for cross-border e-commerce, introduce cross-border e-commerce operators and logistics storage facilities, continue to promote the construction of overseas warehouses and offline experience stores, accelerate the standardization, inspection and testing, cross-border traceability, risk warning and other system construction of cross-border e-commerce comprehensive pilot zones, and build a network system for cross-border e-commerce linkage development. At the same time, it is also necessary to fully leverage the role of the China (Heilongjiang) International Trade "Single Window" platform and the Cross border E-commerce Public Service Platform, further opti-

mize platform services, and smooth the online customs clearance channels for cross-border e-commerce export overseas warehouses, providing strong support for cross-border e-commerce export business.

2.2 The Platforms Strictly Supervising and Punishing Infringing Enterprises, and Protecting Intellectual Property Rights

The concept of protecting intellectual property rights in Russia should be enhanced and the value of the brand should be strengthened. At present, the awareness of intellectual property rights among small and medium-sized cross-border e-commerce enterprises in Heihe City is not strong enough. Improving the legal literacy of enterprises and avoiding the wrong idea of pursuing short-term profits. For self-designed and manufactured products, Chinese patents must be applied for before they are launched. If they are sold across borders, it is necessary to consult local intellectual property laws and patent registration instructions, and apply for intellectual property protection in a timely and accurate manner. In addition, from a long-term perspective, cross-border e-commerce companies need to pay attention to cultivating and protecting their own brands, both to prevent infringement of others' rights and to prevent being infringed upon.

Cross-border e-commerce platforms should establish a dedicated investigation department for intellectual property infringement, equipped with experienced intellectual property professionals, to focus on handling complaints and demands from rights holders. When cross-border e-commerce platforms receive relevant demands from rights holders, they immediately form a special working group to ensure the highest efficiency and fastest response and handling. It is necessary to carefully identify each demand and respond promptly to ensure timely resolution of issues and improvement in processing efficiency. If the claims of the rights holder are not established after examination and the enterprise or merchant has not infringed on the relevant rights of intellectual property, a reasonable written explanation should be provided. This document can serve as evidence for the cross-border e-commerce platform's exemption from liability in subsequent intellectual property litigation. The platforms should actively cooperate and cooperate with the supervision and inspection work of intellectual property infringement investigation and law enforcement departments to ensure smooth communication and jointly safeguard the legitimate rights and interests of intellectual property. At the same time, it should closely cooperate with the customs supervision department, establish a docking platform, share data information in real time, actively provide illegal and criminal clues, and jointly crack down on intellectual property infringement.

By collaborating and strengthening communication and coordination mechanisms, intellectual property security can be jointly protected. Cross-border e-commerce platforms can establish a punishment mechanism for dishonest enterprises, stipulating that enterprises and merchants with infringing behavior are not allowed to join the platform for a certain period of time, which puts pressure on the platform for illegal activities of enterprises and merchants who may infringe.

2.3 Establishing a Sound Cross-border Logistics System and Increasing Intelligent Construction

Under the “dual circulation” pattern, the development and growth of cross-border e-commerce in Heilongjiang Province cannot be separated from the establishment and improvement of the cross-border logistics system. Firstly, it is necessary to further consolidate cross-border transportation channels, strengthen the construction of major cargo transportation hubs, expand new transportation channels, and build a logistics transportation network with wide coverage and high transportation efficiency. At the same time, it is also necessary to actively develop intelligent logistics, build modern logistics platforms, and achieve the intelligence and convenience of logistics systems. Secondly, solving the transportation time difficulties in cross-border logistics still relies on establishing overseas warehouses and border warehouses. It is a must to establish border warehouses at cross-border borders to improve the speed of goods transportation, and establish overseas warehouses abroad to achieve a sales model of overseas marketing and local delivery. Considering the increased warehousing costs, it is necessary to strengthen the management of the warehousing system and create conditions to promote shared warehousing among overseas warehouses, in order to effectively improve delivery efficiency and reduce logistics costs.

The first is to accelerate the intelligent and digital construction of cross-border logistics system. There is a must to fully utilize high-tech means such as big data, cloud computing, and blockchain technology to promote the intelligent and digital transformation of cross-border logistics park centers and traditional cross-border logistics enterprises, in order to reduce service costs, improve service efficiency, and achieve traceability of transportation processes. The second is to further expand cross-border e-commerce freight channels to Russia, increase air freight and mixed passenger and freight postal routes from Heilongjiang Province to major cities within Russia, and reduce logistics costs through large-scale transportation. The third is to increase the construction of overseas warehouses within Russia. For cross-border e-commerce retail business, logis-

tics delivery speed is an important factor affecting overseas consumers' orders. Based on the rigid demand of Russian consumers for daily consumer goods in China, the number of overseas warehouses in Russia should be increased, and the location of overseas warehouses should be reasonably set according to cross-border e-commerce trade data with Russia. Big data analysis technology should be used to reduce the unsold inventory rate of overseas warehouses and improve logistics and distribution efficiency.

Conclusion

Heilongjiang Province, as an important gateway for China's trade with Russia, has unique geographical advantages in developing cross-border e-commerce with Russia. However, issues such as low logistics efficiency, inconvenient payment and settlement, policy differences, and talent shortages have hindered its further development. By optimizing the logistics system, improving payment settlement, strengthening policy support, enhancing enterprise competitiveness, cultivating professional talents, and promoting information technology construction, Heilongjiang Province can effectively solve existing problems and further unleash the potential of cross-border e-commerce with Russia. In the future, with the continuous deepening of Sino-Russian economic and trade cooperation, Heilongjiang Province is expected to become a bridgehead for cross-border e-commerce with Russia, injecting new vitality into Sino-Russian economic cooperation and providing new growth points for the economic revitalization of the Northeast region.

Список литературы / Bibliography

1. Wang Lian, Shi Yan, Research on Heilongjiang-Russia Cross-border Ecommerce Logistics Development [J]. Northern Economy and Trade, 2024. № 10. P. 35-37.
2. Liu Weiwei, Cai Yuanping, Research on the Trade Strategy of Cross border E-commerce Agricultural Products between Heilongjiang Province and Russia [J]. Market Modernization, 2024. № 20. P. 83-85.
3. Li Xiao, Ji Danning, Research on the Development of Cross-border Electronic Commerce between Heilongjiang Province and Russia [J]. Foreign Economic Relations & Trade, 2023. № 6. P. 105-108.
4. Wang Lian, Shi Yan, Research on Heilongjiang-Russia Cross-border Ecommerce Development [J]. Northern Economy and Trade, 2023. № 1. P. 9-12.
5. Luo Liping, Jiang Yong, Research on the Financial Risk Prevention Mechanism of Cross border E-commerce between China and Russia [J]. Marketing Management Review, 2022. № 6. P. 7-9.